

NIRS and Aquaphotomics for the Evaluation of the Efficiency of Solar Dehydration Processes

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Parallel transformation tests on pineapple slices, using a drying (with active fan at the top whose ventilation rate depended on the internal temperature: MIRO' 1) micro-plant and a dehydration (with continuously working fan at the bottom: MIRO' 2) micro-plant (45x45x45 cm) operating with solar energy, were carried out.

The performance of the two micro-plants was compared by collecting samples' spectra with a microNIR1700 spectrometer (VIAVI Srl, Italy) in reflectance mode, over the range 900–1600 nm (50 scans; 125 reading points), at three different times from the beginning of the drying process: 0) process start; 1) during the process [48 hrs]; 2) process end [56 hrs]. Spectra collection took place in triplicates directly on sample slices. The spectral data, converted in absorbance, were pretreated using an MS Excel® spreadsheet (Office 365, Microsoft Italia, Milan, Italy) to verify the suitability of the aquaphotomics approach in evaluating process efficiency. Afterwards, spectral data in the wavelength region from 1300 to 1550 nm underwent statistical processing to build the aquagrams and apply the PCA (95% of confidence level). Data processing was carried out according to Tsenkova R. et al.. The dry matter, titratable acidity (SH°), pH and a_w (water activity) were measured in parallel.

Aquagrams, built up at 0, 48, and 56 hours, highlighted differences among fresh, half-dried, and dried slices. Furthermore, different profiles emerged from different dehydration treatments (MIRO'1; MIRO'2).

PCA could explain about 90% of the total variance in the PC1-PC2 score plot. PC1 (75% variance) resulted in the full separation between fresh and dried products while PC2 pointed out the differences between the two different drying processes.

These preliminary results suggest the applicability of aquaphotomics for continuous monitoring of the fruit drying processes using an adequate NIR probe. Further experiments are already in progress.

Keywords: aquaphotomics, food process, chemometrics, food quality

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